

ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURFACE SURVEY IN THE BUSHEHR PENINSULA 5-14 JUNE 1971

Permission to continue my archaeological surface survey in the Province of the Ports and Islands of the Persian Gulf and Sea of Oman and in Kerman Province was obtained from the Archaeological Service of the Ministry of Culture and Arts on the 17 May 1971 (27/2/1350). The area specified in the Ports and Islands Province namely "Between Bandar Minab and Bandar Daylam, and between Bandar Abbas and Jiruft" includes Bushehr as have my two previous permits.

The extraordinary importance of the Bushehr Peninsula in Sassanian times as the major port on the Persian Coast is demonstrated in my article "Persian Gulf commerce in the Sassanian Period and the first two centuries of Islam", submitted for publication in *Bastan Chenassi va Honar-e Iran* the journal of the Archaeological Service of the Ministry of Culture and Arts. This article was the result of a brief visit to Bushehr in November 1969 together with other survey. It was mentioned in this article that further investigations were necessary in the area.

Therefore on Saturday 5 June (15 Khordad) I arrived in Bushehr accompanied by M.E. Prickett of the University of Harvard. Immediately on arrival I contacted Mr. Yazdani the head of Culture and Arts for Bushehr, and presented him with a photocopy of my letter of permission addressed to the head of Culture and Arts for the Province. Since my

last visit to Bushehr a number of military installations have been built in the Bushehr Peninsula. Since I wished to find out where it was permissible for me to study archaeological sites, and also where military security would not permit it Mr. Yazdani recommended that we visit Brigadier General Meydian the senior military officer on the Peninsula and head of the Air Force there. On leaving Mr. Yazdani's office I visited Mr. Carnet the head of Police in Bushehr in charge of foreigners. I gave him a photocopy of my letter from the Ministry of Culture and Arts, informed him that I wished to conduct archaeological surface survey in the area and would on the next day with Mr. Yazdani visit Brigadier General Meydian. There was never any suggestion that I should visit the chief of the Navy in Bushehr and I did not even know of his existence.

At 8.30 on Sunday 6 June (16 Khordad) Mr. Yazdani and myself visited Brigadier General Meydian in his office. We outlined my plans to the General and desired to find out where if anywhere in the Bushehr Peninsula I might be permitted to continue my archaeological surface survey. I particularly wished to study first the region of Hallileh on the south of the Peninsula where I had noted extensive Sassanian sites in 1969, second the area of Tangac to the east, and third and most important the region of Rishahr and Sabzabad where the great Sassanian city of Rev-Ardashir undoubtedly stood. General Meydian had no objection to my research in the first two areas. He advised that I study these areas first and then submit a list of those places I

intended to visit in the region of Rishahr and Sabzabad including details of every photo I wished to take and my schedule. He promised that he would approve my research in those areas where in his judgement military security was not endangered by my presence, and would send a military policeman with me to ensure that I should not be molested and that I should not photograph military installations.

From the 6 June to the 9 June inclusive I carried out surface survey in the region of Hallileh. On the 10 June (20 Khordad) I prepared a list of those areas near Rishahr I hoped to visit and at 5.30 P.M. presented the list which included no fenced off military areas, with map and a four day schedule to the General who made no alterations to the list as presented to him. A photocopy of the document, with the signature of the General is attached to this report. Survey work was not started till the next day Friday 11 June. On this first day I was accompanied by First Lieutenant Arabi and two airmen, on the second and subsequent days only by aircraftsman Alamshenas.

On the afternoon of Sunday 13 June I visited with Alamshenas the important Elamite mound of Tepe Liyan or Tepe Sabzabad excavated by a French Mission in 1913 and published in Volume 15 of the Memoires de la Delegation Archaeologique en Perse. On the list which General Meydian had approved I specifically mentioned that I wished to photograph this mound (enclosure page 1, four lines from the bottom). On the 13 June I was close to this mound for almost an hour investigating the extent

of Elamite and Sassanian settlement nearby and determining the best angle and light for a photograph. On the route to Tepe Liyan I passed within 150 metres of a military compound. The soldiers there examined the document carried by Alamshenas with the General's signature, and allowed us to proceed. To obtain the optimum light conditions I decided to photograph the mound at 6.30 the next day.

At 6.15 P.M. on Monday 14 June I arrived at Sabzabad and photographed Tepe Liyan which is about 500 metres from the military compound from a spot about 400 metres away. Later I photographed a well head from close up at about 500 metres from the military compound. Alamshenas was with me all the time. At about 6.45 P.M. as I was departing a jeep left the compound we had passed the day before. We waited for the jeep the occupants of which checked the document Alamshenas carried and summoned their superior officer. I had no idea when I visited the site but later found out that the compound belonged not to the Air Force but to the Navy. On the arrival of Captain Moustavian head of the Navy in Bushehr we visited General Meydian since the Navy guard said that I had taken photographs of the Navy enclosure, although the airforceman with me had seen what was photographed. To clear this confusion I emptied my three cameras ~~to Captain~~ in the presence of Captain Moustavian and handed him the film which he passed on to the Air Force. When the films are developed the claims of the Navy guard will be proved to be false. The rolls solely contain photographs of archaeological interest taken at Bushehr and others taken in Shiraz to

illustrate my article on " Persian Gulf Commerce in the Sassanian Period and the first two centuries of Islam".

I gave full details of my occupation and position to Captain Moustavian, and on my request we visited Mr. Yazdani who was most helpful. Captain Moustavian took my passport which was returned the following morning and I was assured that I would hear no more about the difficulty of the night before which was the mistake of the Air Force in allowing me close to naval installations. The military raised no objection to my further survey in Bushehr, but since I did not know where military security areas were situated I considered it wiser to consult the Central Office of Archaeology of the Ministry of Culture before carrying out further work near Bushehr. I asked Mr. Yazdani to make a report to Mr. Pourmand so that the Central Office of Archaeology should be informed of my difficulties with the navy.

The survey which was left uncompleted at this stage had produced in eight days of field work some most important results. First the area of the Sassanian mounds at Rishahr and Hallileh were measured. At Rishahr no less than 214 hectares were mounded and covered in Sassanian pottery, and at Hallileh 169 hectares. Unfortunately work was not completed in measuring the size of the suburbs of Rishahr, but the total area under occupation in the Peninsula in Sassanian times must have been at least 450 hectares. All along the sea shore between Rishahr and Hallileh are a string of individual mounds, on some of

which wall lines and even whole ground plans of buildings can be seen on the surface. When survey ended only one of these had been planned. The nature and size of these buildings and the rich pottery around them suggest that they were the houses, or at least the summer houses of the great men of Rishahr. At Rishahr itself a stone jetty stretches into the sea. In the beach section overlying the jetty are buildings associated with Sassanian pottery indicating that the jetty itself was of Sassanian date or earlier.

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